

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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Workshop Report

I.FAST Workshop on “GHz Rate & Rapid Muon Acceleration for Particle Physics” (GR2M)

WP5.2 Pushing Accelerator Frontiers

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ABSTRACT

An I.FAST Workshop explored how Advanced Accelerator Concepts can jump start Dark Sector Searches and Muon/Pion Acceleration. Promising advanced accelerator technologies are dielectric laser accelerators for single electrons – perhaps also muons – and plasma-wakefield accelerators for muons and pions.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	3
2. DARK MATTER AND DIELECTRIC LASER ACCELERATION	4
3. PLASMA ACCELERATION OF MUONS AND PIONS	7
4. ROADMAP AND PERSPECTIVE	8
5. PARTICIPANTS AND PRESENTATIONS	9

1. Introduction

Close to 20 participants attended the topical workshop on “Gigahertz Rate and Rapid Muon Acceleration” (GR2M), organized by I.FAST¹ Work Package 5.2 “Pushing Accelerator Frontiers” in Bern from 10 to 13 December 2023 (Fig. 1). For dark matter searches, multiple experiments are proposed, involving different classes of experiments (muons vs electrons and positrons, appearance vs disappearance experiments, etc.), and an adequate background rejection is important. Promising advanced accelerator technologies are dielectric laser accelerators for single electrons – perhaps also muons – and plasma-wakefield accelerators for muons and pions.

Figure 1: Participants celebrate the success of the I.FAST GR2M workshop in the town where Albert Einstein made important discoveries. Surprisingly, Albert appeared at the workshop dinner (on the left) to assure the good spirit of the I.FAST event.

¹ Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology (I.FAST); co-funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101004730, <https://ifast-project.eu/>.

2. Dark Matter and Dielectric Laser Acceleration

The first part of the workshop was devoted to the Dark Matter (DM) searches and dielectric laser acceleration. Updating his overview of dark matter searches from 1987 (at that time the subject of dark matter, e.g. axions, was not as popular as today), Witek Krasny of LPNHE Paris presented an intriguing overview of cosmological and astrophysical evidence for dark matters, experimental constraints, and accelerator-based dark matter searches. Starting from the Einstein equation, and the special case considered by Robertson and Walker, he discussed the cosmological evidence for dark matter based on microwave background and Supernova data, covering the length scales of 1 Mpc to 14 Gpc (the size of the visible universe). At lesser length scales, astrophysical observations hinting at dark matter include the rotational velocity distributions in galaxies, gravitational lensing, and colliding galaxies. Astrophysics also offers some indications for warm dark matter in the 2-10 keV energy range. Particle physics addresses the question of dark matter by extending its Standard Model with weakly interacting DM particles. Witek offered three possible conclusions, ranging from optimistic to pessimistic (cold dark matter WIMPS exist at the 1 TeV scale; experiments are going to the neutrino floor; no dark matter exists). He next illustrated, and reinvented, the neutron and neutrino discoveries as earlier example discoveries of “dark particles”. The reason why the journal Nature rejected Fermi’s epochal paper was revealing.

Some dark matter experiments are looking for an appearance that requires a high flux of incoming particles. For electrons, the standard is set by BDX at JLAB, for protons by the proposed SHIP experiment at CERN, and photons by the proposed Gamma Factory at CERN. In addition, appearances could be seen at existing collider experiments such as the LHC at CERN. Other dark matter experiments search for disappearance. They rely on DC-like e-beam. Prominent examples are LDMX at SLAC and the newly proposed DLA-DMX at PSI, scrutinized at the present workshop. DC-like muon-beam can be explored by the M3 experiment at FNAL, which was also presented during the workshop.

In the end of his mesmerizing presentation, Witek arrived at proposing a minimal, and possibly sufficient, set of five future DM experiments: 1) An experiment with the highest flux of electrons (such as BDX at JLAB with 10^{22} e/target); 2) an experiment with the highest flux on protons (such as SHIP at CERN with 2×10^{20} p/target, and/or MicroBooNE at FNAL with 7×10^{20} p/target); 3) an experiment with the highest flux of photons (Gamma Factory at CERN with 10^{25} γ /target); 4) An experiment with a DC-like beam of electrons which would be rather insensitive to a large beam spot and beam divergence (such as LDMX at SLAC with of order 2×10^{16} e/target); and 5) the existing collider experiments with a High Level Trigger event building rate upgrade (such as ATLAS, CMS and LHCb at the LHC – these upgrades, should, in Witek’s view, precede the construction of dedicated experiments looking at the IPs of the existing LHC experiments from a long distance). Future collider experiments were hinted at by the table patterns of local restaurants (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Apparent layout of future colliders with multiple interaction points seen in a Bernese restaurant (Courtesy Uwe Niedermayer).

Paolo Crivelli from ETH Zürich discussed the NA64 experiment as one of the most prominent examples of ongoing accelerator-based dark matter searches and presented the first results using a high-energy muon beam [[arXiv 2401.01708](https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.01708)]. The proposed LDMX experiment at SLAC, presented, on invitation, by Silke Möbius from the University Bern, may set a new standard for indirect dark matter searches. Frank Zimmermann of CERN discussed the associated DASEL/LDMX accelerator based on LCLS-II. Fascinatingly, advanced concepts employing dielectric laser acceleration, in particular when integrating the accelerating structure with the laser oscillator, could achieve many orders of magnitude higher rates of single high-energy electrons entering into an LDMX-type detector.

Uwe Niedermayer of TU Darmstadt, Stefanie Kraus from the University Erlangen-Nürnberg, and Raziye Dadashi of PSI and EPFL Lausanne reviewed and illustrated the present state of the art of dielectric laser acceleration (DLA) plus future plans. Yves Bellouard, also from EPFL, discussed advances in high repetition-rate lasers and micro/nano-structures, which made the proposed

combined laser-accelerator structures appear to be within reach. Of course, the detector time resolution would also need to be improved tremendously to keep pace with the higher rate of the accelerator.

More specifically, Raziye Dadashi recalled that dark matter is searched by following either of two main directions. The first is the direct search with a visible DM decay back into the Standard Model, with interaction probability of $\sim \varepsilon^4$, where ε denotes the coupling constant between dark and normal matter. Due to the fourth power of the small coupling parameter, a very large number of primary particles are needed ($\sim 10^{20}$ electrons on target). The second approach is the indirect search which detects a missing energy or momentum. This approach has an interaction probability of $\sim \varepsilon^2$, and its application requires less particles in total, but instead a very clean, well-characterized initial state. This can be pursued through the production of single electrons at a high repetition rate. Indirect dark matter searches call, e.g., for a beam with an energy of 10-20 GeV (20 m long dielectric structure with 1 GeV/m energy gradient), and single electrons with a repetition rate of 10 GHz.

Dielectric Laser Acceleration (DLA) relies on a structure with submicron features driven by an incoming electromagnetic laser wave. Similar to a conventional microwave linac, the laser wave drives the DLA structure in resonance with the motion of the electrons, thereby leading to acceleration. The dynamics is studied using the code DLATRACK6D, developed by Uwe Niedermayer, which can efficiently model the alternating-phase focusing in all 3 dimensions. Currently, at PSI, a structure with 2 micron period is being designed and optimized using a genetic algorithm. An energy gradient of 2.14 GeV/m is achieved in simulations. Passing through a 7 mm long structure consisting of 3500 cells, a 1 GeV beam is accelerated by 14 MeV with a final energy spread of less 2×10^{-5} . The structure was optimized not only for low energy spread, but also for high survival rate, achieving 100% transmission after the optimisation. A single-electron source similar to those used in electron microscopes is considered, with a repetition rate of 3 GHz; the expected normalized beam emittance of 10 pm from the source is suitable for the 400 nm aperture, even taking into account the field non-uniformity. The energy efficiency and repetition rate are boosted by recirculating the laser pulse through the structure, that is by making the latter part of the laser oscillator, as originally proposed by Bob Siemann.

Stefanie Kraus gave a presentation on the DLA state-of-the-art and recent experiments. The “accelerator on a chip” (ACHIP) ingredients are: 1) electron sources that provide sub-nanometer emittances; 2) accelerator structures formed by lensing, staging, and gating; 3) a scalability feature, which affects the confinement and laser power delivery. The operating principle involves acceleration, deceleration, and deflection. The accelerator structures have evolved from bonded silica gratings (2013) over silicon pillar structures (2015) to finally arrive at vertically pumped systems (2021). Stefanie also discussed the guiding concept of alternating phase focusing, namely that the laser phase in the structure is regularly flipped – through the design of the structure – so as to alternate between focusing and defocusing in each plane. Further advances are possible through coherent laser acceleration obtained by combining phase jumps and tapering. Staged structures presently under construction feature peak surface fields of 600 to 700 MV/m and a design

accelerating gradient of 22.7 MV/m. Experiments and simulations with a particular short structure both show a maximum energy gain of 12.3 keV. Stefanie's talk also summarized the worldwide DLA activities: the ACHIP collaboration includes SLAC, Stanford, UCLA, Darmstadt, DESY, FAU, PSI, and Hamamatsu. Other DLA research groups are in Liverpool, Wroclaw, Nanjing (NUAA), U. Tokyo.

Uwe Niedermayer highlighted that for future applications a key property of the DLA will be the length scalability. The two main issues are 1) the laser synchronization over long distances, and 2) the electron confinement in tiny channels (ca. 400 nm aperture). The typical length for a 1 MeV DLA injector is around 1 cm with an energy gradient of 500 MeV/m (based on, e.g., fused silica structures). Uwe reviewed tilted laser pulses incident on DLA structure and the issue of electron confinement, citing Earnshaw's theorem. It was pointed out that electron confinement, in particular, is an issue at low energy. The physical interaction of the electromagnetic field and the particle beam can be simulated by Uwe's DLATRACK6D code, which allows the modelling of any periodic structure. This code applies one wake kick per DLA cell. Uwe discussed the alternating phase focusing (APF) and the creation of a buncher based on DLA structures. The DLA structures for Stanford are designed for 70 and 100 MeV/m peak gradients (35 and 50 MeV/m average gradient), which enables sub-relativistic acceleration with high energy gain. The 3D APF will overcome the length limitation of the 2D structures, but this approach requires a consistent design of the Courant-Snyder lattice in all 3 dimensions. Uwe also discussed the challenges associated with electron tracking on a femtosecond time scale. The problem is that tiny electron bunches and huge fields can render the tracking simulations prohibitively slow. A possible solution consists in adopting a "moving window" tracker which provides 1) multiple static or frequency domain fields; 2) a clustered particle vector (direct particle-particle space-charge interaction) and 3) statistics as in a many-shot experiment. The "FemtoTrack" with space charge was compared with measurements from the Stanford "glassbox".

3. Plasma Acceleration of Muons and Pions

The second part of the workshop was devoted to the plasma acceleration of non-ultra-relativistic and rapidly decaying particles, like muons and pions. Vladimir Shiltsev of FNAL and Daniel Schulte of CERN presented the case of muon collider, tentative parameters, ongoing R&D efforts, and the muon acceleration requirements. Vladimir Shiltsev also discussed the intriguing possibility of low emittance muon sources based on plasma-wakefield accelerators. Alexander Pukhov from Heine University Düsseldorf and Chiara Badiali from IST Lisbon discussed how plasma acceleration could bring non-relativistic slow particles, such as muons, to relativistic velocities. One particular challenge is the need to slow down the phase velocity of the plasma wake to match the speed of the particles. This can be achieved, for example, by using spatio-temporal laser pulses to slow down the driver, by varying the plasma density profile to control the velocity of the wake, or by a combination thereof. Chiara presented detailed simulations of the beam dynamics of muons and pions in a plasma wake, allowing her to demonstrate that even pions could be accelerated to relativistic velocities with a reasonable survival rate.

The workshop fostered numerous heated discussions and uncovered unresolved issues, which include the “Bern controversy” regarding the ultimate limits of luminosity for PeV energies. Muons are considered particles of choice for future accelerators at the energy frontier. Both low-energy and high-energy muons have useful applications. Is there an Angstrom limit to the beam diameter? Are tiny beta functions possible? Can plasmas help to overcome such limitations? Understanding and modelling the non-point-like particle luminosity is another important topic, also relevant for the Gamma Factory. In this context, the Pomeranchuk effect was mentioned.

4. Roadmap and Perspective

The final discussions at the GR2M Workshop assembled the following roadmap and perspective.

The DLA studies are to be maintained and, if possible, accelerated; the application of DLAs to LDMX type of experiments is recommended; the scalability of energy from staging needs to be demonstrated and so is the integration of the accelerator structure inside the laser oscillator. Different time scales are anticipated for the proposed demonstrator experiments. Concerning DLAs, a reasonable target is achieving a gradient of 500 MeV/m and an energy gain of 0.05 GeV in 5 years on a single wafer, possibly at UCLA, in Erlangen, or at DESY. The demonstration of an integrated DLA laser oscillator could be foreseen at the EPFL in 5 to 7 years from now. The required technology already exists, but “blowing power” through a tube can be a challenge. Plasma-wakefield acceleration of muons could conceivably be tested either at CERN-AWAKE or at PSI. It was proposed, as a first step, to put a solid target or tape into the AWAKE set up, on a time scale of 5 years. A proposal for a low-energy muon source would be timely by 2025, as input for the next *European Strategy update*.

The Gamma factory was recognized as an intense source of polarized muons and positrons. For muon acceleration studies the dephasing issue, linked to the muons’ non-ultrarelativistic energy, seems to be resolved. A demonstrator experiment for muon plasma acceleration is called for. Open questions are when and where? A (pre-)cooled muon beam would be useful to test the final cooling at PSI, FNAL, and CERN (injecting muons into AWAKE). This effort does not look straightforward. For example, the Tevatron could be converted into a Gamma factory (with optical laser replaced by FELs).

Citing one of his friends, at the end of the workshop Witek Krasny advised the audience: “Don’t be obsessed with the Nobel Prize, it brings more harm than good”.

5. Participants and Presentations

The GR2M workshop was attended by 16 expert participants hailing from diverse laboratories and universities: CERN / Switzerland (2) ; Ecole Polytechnique / France (1) ; EPFL / Switzerland (3) ; ETH Zürich (1) ; FNAL / USA (1) ; Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg / Germany (1) ; Heinrich-Heine Universität Düsseldorf / Germany (1) ; PSI / Switzerland (2) ; Sorbonne University Paris / France (1) ; TU Darmstadt / Germany (1) ; University of Bern / Switzerland (1) ; and University of Lisbon / Portugal (1).

The workshop programme and all presentations can be found on the web at <https://indico.psi.ch/event/14790/> .